

ENERGY EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS OF THE MADGRAPH EVENT GENERATOR FOR HIGH ENERGY PHYSICS

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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CERN’s environmental strategy is built on three pillars: minimizing the laboratory’s environmental impact, reducing energy consumption while increasing energy reuse, and developing technologies that contribute to global sustainability.

This project focused on the study of the power consumption and energy usage of MG5_aMC@NLO event generator (MadGraph), with the aim of assessing its environmental implications.

We employed Single Instruction Multiple Threads (SIMT) GPUs (NVIDIA V100/A100), and Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) CPUs, with, e.g., AVX2 instruction sets, to execute various processes. Event generation was carried out using MadGraph, and power consumption was systematically recorded during the runs. The recorded power data can then be used to calculate energy usage, from which the corresponding CO₂ emissions can be estimated, which would further provide insights into the environmental impact of these computational processes.

ABSTRACT

The objective of this project is to study the performance and energy consumption of Monte Carlo event generators used in high-energy physics simulations. The project builds upon ongoing efforts to optimize event generators such as MadGraph, evaluating their performance across various computational technologies, including GPU acceleration, and CPU-based acceleration using vector instructions. The work involves the use of monitoring tools to gain insights into hardware utilization, memory efficiency, and power consumption. This research has broader implications for the high-energy physics community, addressing the need for sustainable computational practices, and optimized computing infrastructure. It also offers the opportunity to contribute to cutting-edge research at the CERN IT department, collaborating with a team of experienced researchers.

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1 Introduction

High-energy physics research depends on large-scale computing, which consumes significant energy and contributes to CERN's environmental footprint. To address this, CERN's strategy focuses on minimizing impact, reducing and reusing energy, and developing sustainable technologies [1]. According to ATLAS 2022 Computing model, 20% of the computing resource will be occupied for event generation [2, 3] during HL-LHC.

Event generators such as MadGraph [4, 5] and SHERPA [6] are central parts of particle physics simulations, but they can be computationally intensive. This project investigates the power consumption and energy usage of MadGraph on different architectures: SIMT GPUs (NVIDIA) and SIMD CPUs (with architectures AVX2 and AVX-512).

This study is made possible by the recent release of the CUDACPP plugin for MadGraph [7], which enables offloading matrix element computations to both SIMT and SIMD hardware. Section 2 provides an overview of MadGraph, followed by subsections introducing the new plugin and the relevant GPU and CPU architectures. Subsequent sections describe our methodology for power measurements, including manual runs of the MadEvent generator, execution with gridpacks (see section 3.1.2), and tests performed on a cluster. We also present the results derived from the measurements and outline the procedure for converting power usage into energy consumption, which would enable the calculation of the associated CO₂ numbers.

The results offer insights into how computational choices affect environmental impact and highlight opportunities for more sustainable practices in high-energy physics computing.

2 The MadGraph Event Generator

MadGraph is a Monte Carlo event generator widely used in particle physics to simulate collisions and study fundamental interactions. It allows users to define initial and final states of several processes, generate the corresponding Feynman diagrams, write the mathematical code related to them, and compute the key physical quantities such as cross sections. Using the generated code, MadGraph's event generator MadEvent produces events, that are then written on LHEF [8]. The event generator is run automatically through a Python orchestration layer, that can be executed via the command-line interface that MadGraph provides.

MadGraph is a code generator written in Python that can initially produce source code in FORTRAN, C, and C++ for the calculations. To incorporate hardware acceleration through SIMD and SIMT, new implementations using C++ vector instructions and GPU programming have been introduced. The first step towards hardware acceleration involved identifying the primary performance bottleneck. Profiling revealed that matrix element evaluation consumed the majority of runtime during event generation. This portion of the code was subsequently rewritten to leverage CPU vectorization and GPU computing, using CUDA for NVIDIA GPUs or HIP for AMD GPUs, significantly improving computational efficiency.

2.1 The CUDACPP plugin

These new efforts have been incorporated in the MadGraph plugin CUDACPP [7]. The plugin has two new output modes:

- `madevent_gpu`: to run processes on GPUs;
- `madevent_simd`: to run processes using vectorized CPU instructions.

We installed the CUDACPP plugin in MadGraph, by starting MadGraph and typing:


```
mg5> install cudacpp
```

The plugin allows us to set the computational backend in the `run_card.dat`, or through the interactive interface. Listing 1 shows how to generate a process in MadGraph and store it in a folder using the `output` command, here specifically in `PROC_pp_ttx_gpu`. It also illustrates how to set the `cudacpp_backend` to `cuda`. The plugin additionally accepts the following values, which are self-explanatory: `fortran`, `cpp`, `cppnone`, `cppavx2`, `cpp512y`.

```
1 import model sm
2 generate p p > t t~
3 output madevent_gpu PROC_pp_ttx_gpu
4 launch PROC_pp_ttx_gpu
5 set cudacpp_backend cuda
```

Listing 1: MadGraph commands for GPU execution.

2.2 Computing Architecture

These simulations are computationally demanding. Modern high-performance computing relies on a variety of architectures to execute instructions and process data efficiently. The choice of the computing architecture, within the characteristics of the algorithm in place, may impact significantly the execution time, and, as a result, the power consumption. In this study, we analyzed the differences in power consumption from the use of two complementary paradigms: SIMD and SIMT, comparing them with the original Fortran-based approach.

2.2.1 SIMD CPUs

In a Single Instruction, Single Data (SISD) CPU, each instruction operates on a single data element at a time. While simple and effective for sequential tasks, SISD is inefficient for large-scale scientific computations where the same operation must be applied repeatedly across many data elements.

SIMD architectures, in contrast, allow a single instruction to be applied simultaneously to multiple data elements. Modern CPUs implement SIMD through vector instruction sets such as AVX2 and AVX-512, which enable operations on e.g. multiple floating-point values in a single cycle. MadGraph allows the user to select the architecture they want to compile the code against, or to automatically select the best one according to the system (using the setting `cppauto`) SIMD. Fig. 1 shows how data is processed in sequential and parallel structure. The leftmost one shows one input and one output per cycle in a SISD architecture and the rightmost shows N inputs and N outputs per cycle in a SIMD architecture.

2.2.2 SIMT GPUs

Alongside SIMD CPUs, Single Instruction, Multiple Threads (SIMT) GPUs provide another layer of parallelism for high-performance computing. SIMT extends the idea of SIMD to thousands of lightweight threads running concurrently on a GPU. These threads are organized into

Figure 1: Sequential vs parallel data processing, figure from [9].

groups called warps (typically 32 threads on NVIDIA GPUs), which execute the same instruction. While each thread has its own registers and can follow a unique control path, divergence within a warp can reduce efficiency since different branches must be synchronized. GPUs also feature a deep memory hierarchy, with registers, shared memory, and high-bandwidth global memory, making efficient memory access patterns essential for maximizing throughput.

In this project, we primarily employed NVIDIA GPUs to execute the generated CUDA code through the CUDACPP plugin. This plugin leverages the SIMT execution model to map physics computations onto thousands of threads, enabling high throughput and efficient utilization of GPU resources. By exploiting the parallelism of SIMT, the computationally intensive tasks in our workflow—such as matrix element evaluations—benefit from significant acceleration compared to CPU-only execution.

3 Methodology

3.1 Preliminary tests

Initially, to monitor power consumption by both the GPU and CPU, we used a shared virtual machine hosted on CERN infrastructure, equipped with an NVIDIA V100 GPU, and with an Intel® Xeon® Silver 4216 CPU. We performed these tests as preliminary tests and used a cluster later on. We run the MadGraph generated code in two modes.

3.1.1 Running the MadEvent generator manually

A subprocess refers to a specific interaction or scattering process that occurs within the quark or parton structure of a particle during a particular high-energy reaction or collision. The MadEvent generator can be run manually for each subprocess that is generated by MadGraph. In this scenario, events will be generated only for the single subprocess selected, and only for one single phase space configuration. This mode gives us the liberty of testing the code and the monitoring tools. The MadEvent entry point is a single binary with the name `madevent_<backend>`, where `<backend>` can be one among `cuda`, `fortran`, `avx2`, etc. It additionally requires standard input to specify parameters like the number of events to generate, the amount of iterations, as well as the phase space configuration to use. The first compilation of the subprocesses should be done by running `./bin/generate_events`, so that all jobs for each

subprocess are created. Then, in each $P_{<n>}$ folder, multiple subfolders $G_{<n>}$ would be created, each one containing a certain parametrization of the parameter space. Additionally, they contain the file `input_app.txt` that lists the standard input to give to the `madevent` executable. The latter is created in each $P_{<n>}$ folder, and it will be a symlink to the `madevent_{<backend>}` executable. For example, in the case of `cuda` backend, we executed `madevent_cuda < input_app.txt`, passing the standard input through the file `input_app.txt` as shown in Listing 2. A sample of `input_app.txt`, which sets the parameters for running MadEvent, is shown in Listing 3. The comments explain the purpose of each line. MadEvent runs only the phase space configuration specified in the last line. The first line indicates the number of events to be generated, while the next two numbers specify the number of repetitions of the process. MadEvent repeats this process iteratively until it reaches the desired accuracy, as indicated by the second line in Listing 3. The remaining parameters are not relevant for the purposes of our project.

```
./madevent < G<n>/input_app.txt
```

Listing 2: `madevent` execution

```
16384    1    1    ! Number of events and max and min iterations
0.01    ! Accuracy
2       ! Grid Adjustment 0=none, 2=adjust
1       ! Suppress Amplitude 1=yes
0       ! Helicity Sum/event 0=exact
1       ! Phase space configuration to consider
```

Listing 3: `input_app.txt` file

While running the `madevent` executable, GPU power consumption was monitored using `nvidia-smi`, with the command:

```
nvidia-smi --query-gpu=timestamp,power.draw,utilization.gpu
↪ --format=csv,noheader,nounits --loop-ms=500
```

storing the measurements in a CSV file. The tool `nvidia-smi` is a command-line utility provided by NVIDIA that reports GPU status and performance metrics such as utilization, memory usage, temperature, and power consumption. In this case, we chose the process $g g \rightarrow t \bar{t} g g$ for our initial test because the computation of matrix element of the process takes a good fraction of time. We are constrained to use a single channel processes because each `madevent` executable runs only one single subprocess. In this subprocess, two gluons interact to produce a top-antitop pair ($t \bar{t}$) along with three additional gluons.

3.1.2 Using gridpacks

One of the main users of event generators like MadGraph are the CERN LHC experiments. They generate large number of events, and typically run the event generation pipeline using

gridpacks. Gridpacks are precompiled packages that bundle multiple subprocesses together, and contain already all the required information to generate events. Since we wanted to apply our techniques to real world scenarios, we switched to using gridpacks from running MadEvent manually. To enable them, the option `gridpack` must be set to `True` in the run card. All subprocesses are then saved in a single archive file that can be executed collectively. The archive contains the entry point executable script `run.sh` to launch the run and generate events. In our scenario, we chose the multi-process event `p p > t t~ g g g` which is the extended version of the single-channel process we used in the previous case and we followed the steps detailed below:

1. Generate the desired process using MadGraph, using `madevent_gpu` for exporting with GPU support and `madevent_simd` for exporting with vectorized CPU support.
2. Save the process in a directory (e.g., `PROC_pp_ttxggg_gpu`) and set `gridpack=True` while launching it to enable gridpack generation.
3. After generation, a compressed gridpack file is created inside the process directory. Unzip this file to obtain the execution script `run.sh`.
4. Run the gridpack with: `./run.sh <events number> <seed number>`.

The Listing 4 and 5 show Python scripts that utilize the generated gridpacks to run the events. For what concerns power measurements:

- GPU + Host Power logging (CUDA backend): To log GPU power consumption during the execution of `./run.sh <events number> <seed number>`, we synchronized the GPU monitoring with `nvidia-smi` with the event generation process, and we saved the readings in a CSV file as shown in Listing 4.

In the same way, the host power was logged in parallel with GPU power, using host monitoring tools.

- Host Power logging (vectorized CPU backends): For vectorized CPUs (AVX2, AVX-512), host power consumption was recorded using host monitoring tools.

In both cases, we ensured that the script automatically terminated and stopped recording host power measurements once the run of the gridpack had finished (see Listing 5).


```

1  # Execute ./run.sh <event num> <seed number>
2
3  def log_gpu_stats(proc_running_flag):
4      nvsmi_cmd = [
5          "nvidia-smi",
6          "--query-gpu='{','.join(fields)}'",
7          "--format=csv,noheader,nounits",
8          "--loop-ms=500"
9      ]
10
11     with open(log_file, mode="w", newline="") as f:
12         writer = csv.writer(f)
13         writer.writerow(["date", "timestamp", "utilization.gpu [%]",
14             ↪ "power.draw [W]"])
15
16         try:
17             nvsmi_proc = subprocess.Popen(
18                 nvsmi_cmd, stdout=subprocess.PIPE,
19                 stderr=subprocess.DEVNULL, text=True
20             )
21
22             for line in nvsmi_proc.stdout:
23                 # Here, we write in the CSV file
24
25         finally:
26             nvsmi_proc.kill()
27
28     # Shared flag to signal app status
29     proc_running_flag = {"running": True}
30
31     # Start GPU logging in a background thread
32     gpu_logger = threading.Thread(target=log_gpu_stats,
33     ↪ args=(proc_running_flag,))
34     gpu_logger.start()
35
36     # Run your application
37     print("Starting GPU app...")
38     app_proc = subprocess.Popen(app_cmd, shell=True)
39     app_proc.wait()
40
41     # Signal logger to stop
42     proc_running_flag["running"] = False
43     gpu_logger.join()
44     print("Logging complete.")

```

Listing 4: Logging GPU power.


```

1 def is_gpu_app_running():
2     try:
3         result = subprocess.run(
4             ["ssh", gpu_host, gpu_check_cmd],
5             stdout=subprocess.DEVNULL,
6             stderr=subprocess.DEVNULL
7         )
8         return result.returncode == 0
9     except Exception:
10        return False
11
12 def get_ipmi_power():
13     now = datetime.now()
14     date_str = now.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")
15     time_str = now.strftime("%H:%M:%S.%3f")[:-3]
16     try:
17         result = subprocess.run(
18             command, # this is an internal command defined for the host under
19                 ↪ examination
20             stdout=subprocess.PIPE,
21             stderr=subprocess.PIPE,
22             text=True,
23             timeout=5
24         )
25         for line in result.stdout.splitlines():
26             if "Instantaneous power reading" in line:
27                 power = line.strip().split()[3]
28                 return (date_str, time_str, power)
29         return (date_str, time_str, "N/A")
30     except subprocess.TimeoutExpired:
31         return (date_str, time_str, "Timeout")
32
33 # Start logging
34 log_file = "cpu_power_log.csv"
35 with open(log_file, "w") as f:
36     # Here we write the power in the CSV file

```

Listing 5: Logging host power.

3.2 Using a dedicated cluster node for power measurements

Using the virtual machine hosted at CERN allowed us to carry out our tests systematically and understand what are the best ways to measure the power draw from the GPU and the host. However, being the node a virtual machine on a shared infrastructure meant that other users might be running tasks on the same host at the same time, affecting the results on power measurements. To address this, we decided to use a dedicated environment for CPU power measurements. This was achieved using the Calcul Intensif et Stockage de Masse (CISM)

cluster, hosted in Belgium.

The CISM cluster was created in 2004 at Université Catholique de Louvain (UCLouvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium) by users of the HPC facilities from various departments of the university. CISM operates the scientific computing clusters and data storage systems installed at UCLouvain, organizes and delivers HPC training sessions for researchers, and provides consultancy and expertise in code porting, optimization, compilation, and related areas.

The CISM cluster is based on the Slurm Workload Manager. Thanks to the `exclusive` flag, we could ensure that the entire node would be allocated solely for our use. Jobs were submitted through Slurm scripts specifying the required CPU cores, memory, and runtime, ensuring that our power measurements and simulations ran efficiently without interference from other users. Additionally, we performed the measurements on the single node `mb-mil101`, which is equipped with an NVIDIA A100 GPU. This allowed us to maintain consistent and reproducible execution environments for both GPU and CPU processes. We also decided later on to sample the GPU power in the cluster using `nvidia-smi` since the GPU power measurements were sampled every 5 minutes in the cluster and we wanted more frequent power measurements with `nvidia-smi`.

We decided to start with a simpler process `g g > t t~ ng` and `u u~ > e+ e- ng` (with `n` being an integer number in between 0, 1, 2), because we are limited by the scheduling system in the cluster, and, before scaling up our measurements to more complicated processes, we wanted to get a first set of measurements on smaller, more manageable and faster workloads. The extension to more complicated processes would then be trivial and would require us to run the codebases again but with a different process.

4 Results

4.1 Power measurements from the virtual machine

The GPU and CPU power measurements obtained from our initial tests with `cuda` backend are included below. The first section shows the result obtained by running `madevent_cuda < input_app.txt` for `g g > t t~ g g g` and the second section shows the result obtained by running with `gridpacks` for `p p > t t~ g g g`.

The GPU shows a cyclic workload pattern, with utilization alternating between 0% and 100%. Events are run in batches and sent to the GPU which processes and returns them to the host. This causes the fluctuations seen in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. It can be seen that the power draw fluctuates between ~ 75 W (idle) and around ~ 200 W (active), indicating bursts of computation followed by idle periods. Here, we used 10^6 events to run the process manually and with `gridpacks` for our initial tests. The maximum power of the NVIDIA V100 GPU is 250 W and the figures show that the maximum GPU power reached around ~ 200 W.

4.1.1 Executing MadEvent manually

Fig. 2 shows the GPU power consumption and utilization for a single-process channel `g g > t t~ g g g` obtained with `madevent_cuda < input_app.txt`. The `input_app.txt` file can be found inside the folder `SubProcesses/P1_gg_ttxggg` where the process-specific files are saved.

Figure 2: GPU power and utilization for $g g > t \bar{t} g g g$ using MadEvent.

4.1.2 Executing with Gridpacks

We also measured the GPU power and utilization for the process $p p > t \bar{t} g g g$ using gridpacks. Fig. 3 shows the power draw and utilization for the first 120 s and last 120 s for $p p > t \bar{t} g g g$ (the middle part has the same trend that appears in this plot). The main difference between the two panels resides in the fact that the last 120 s show the end of the run, with the event generation finishing, and the final processing happening (results files and LHEF event file are written).

Figure 3: GPU power and utilization for $p p > t \bar{t} g g g$ using gridpacks.

We can produce a similar plot for the host power, which can be connected to the CPU power draw. Fig. 4 shows the power consumed by the host. The host power consumption increases from a baseline of ~ 700 W to fluctuating values between 800 W and 900 W during event processing. The fluctuations reflect varying CPU load as gridpack events are processed. Once the computation ends, the power draw gradually decreases back toward the baseline level.

However, since the machine we used was shared, we cannot be fully confident in the accuracy of the power measurements. Therefore, we decided to continue our efforts on a dedicated environment in the CISM cluster.

Figure 4: Host power draw for $p p > t \bar{t} g g$ using gridpacks.

4.2 Power measurement using CISM Cluster

Since the CISM cluster provides a dedicated environment for power measurements, we submitted the jobs to it using the Slurm commands shown in Listing 6. The node supported CUDA, FORTRAN, and AVX2, so we restricted our runs to these three computational backends. We tested single-process channels (exported in gridpacks), namely $g g > t \bar{t} n g$ and $u \bar{u} > e^+ e^- n g$, where n ranges from 0 to 2. The subsequent section describes the methods we implemented for running jobs on the cluster. First, we explain how we automated the creation of gridpacks, and second, how we automated different processes for running a specified number of events.

```

1 #SBATCH --partition=gpu
2 #SBATCH --odelist=mb-mil101
3 #SBATCH --exclusive
4 #SBATCH --gres=gpu:1
5 #SBATCH --job-name=RemRun
6 #SBATCH --output=logs/RemRun_%j.out
7 #SBATCH --cpus-per-task=4
8 #SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=1G

```

Listing 6: Slurm commands.

4.2.1 Gridpack creation

The generation of gridpacks for the three backends and processes was automated using a shell script, as presented in Listing 7. In this workflow, the backend and process parameters were provided as command-line arguments from a separate shell script, which contained the Slurm submission command `#SBATCH` (see Listing 8).

```
1 backend=$1
2 shift
3 process="$@"
4
5 genfile="generate_${process_name}_${backend}"
6
7 cat > "$genfile" <<EOF
8 generate $process
9 EOF
10
11 if [ $backend == "cuda" ]; then
12     echo "output madevent_gpu ${process_name}_${backend} -nojpeg" >> $genfile
13 else
14     echo "output madevent_simd ${process_name}_${backend} -nojpeg" >> $genfile
15 fi
16
17 echo "launch" >> $genfile
18 echo "set gridpack True" >> $genfile
19 echo "set cudacpp_backend $backend" >> $genfile
```

Listing 7: Automating gridpacks creation.


```

1  ##define processes
2  for process in "${processes[@]}"; do
3      jprocess_name=$(echo "$process" | xargs python -c "import sys; print(
   ↪  '.join(sys.argv[1:]).replace('>', '_').replace('~', 'x').replace('
   ↪  ', '_') )")
4  for backend in $backends; do
5      if [ $backend == "cuda" ]; then
6          sbatch --partition=gpu --exclusive --gres=gpu:1
   ↪  --job-name=${process_name}_${backend}
   ↪  --output=logs/${process_name}_${backend}_%j.out
   ↪  producing_gridpack.sh $backend $process
7      else
8          sbatch --partition=gpu --job-name=${process_name}_${backend}
   ↪  --output=logs/${process_name}_${backend}_%j.out
   ↪  producing_gridpack.sh $backend $process
9      fi
10     done
11 done

```

Listing 8: Submitting jobs for gridpack creation using Slurm.

4.2.2 Running the event generation

After creating the gridpacks, we automated the events generation for the different processes and backends, as shown in Listing 9. We also run each combination of process and backend multiple times by varying the option `-p` of the gridpack executable, which selects how many different MadEvent instances are running in parallel.

A sleep interval was introduced between runs to allow the CPU to cool down, ensuring that the conditions of each measurement were consistent. This made it possible to compare results across different runs and allowed the CPU to return to its idle state before starting new processes for each backend and `p`. The script start and end times were recorded in the log file along with the individual process and backend start and end times so that we could then match the timestamped power measurements sampled server side, and request the power measurements from the cluster afterwards.


```

1  ##slurm commands go here
2  ##define processes, backends, and number of events
3
4  echo "Starting full script at $(date +"%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S")"
5
6  for process in "${processes[@]}"; do
7      ##define process name here
8      for backend in $backends; do
9          echo "=== Running for backend: $backend and process: $process_name
10         ↪ ==="
11         ##command to change directory and unpack the zip file
12         for p in 4 2 1; do
13             echo "Sleeping for $sleep_time s before running $backend with p:
14             ↪ $p, for process: $process_name"
15             sleep $sleep_time
16             echo "Starting running with p: $p, for process: $process_name
17             ↪ with $backend at $(date +"%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S")"
18             ./run.sh -p $p $n_events 24
19             echo "Ending running with p: $p, for process: $process_name with
20             ↪ $backend at $(date +"%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S")"
21         done
22     done
23 done
24
25 echo "Ending Full script at $(date +"%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S")"

```

Listing 9: Running events generation with Slurm.

4.2.3 Power measurements and CSV file creation

We obtained the power measurements from the cluster, as shown in Listing 10. To facilitate later analysis, specifically for producing GPU and CPU power plots, we prepared a script to separate the GPU and CPU power readings from the cluster's power measurement file, as illustrated in Listing 11. The elapsed time for each process and backend was calculated from the log file (lines 10–28 in Listing 11). The start and end times for each process and backend were then recorded from the log file and matched with the timestamps in the cluster's power measurement file (lines 30–39 in Listing 11), which allowed us to extract the corresponding power consumption within that interval for each process, backend, and number of simultaneous MadEvent instances.

The CSV file that was produced from the Listing 11 contains the power and elapsed time for each process and backend with different values of the `-p` flag. Finally, one could use this CSV file to produce plots of power for different values of `-p`, backend and process. For the GPU runs, we additionally recorded power using `nvidia-smi`. The data from the cluster still requires processing. The next step is a systematic analysis of the cluster's power measurements, for which the team already has the relevant data.


```
1 2025-08-16 23:59:40 1755381580 199 "mb-mil101: Check Power"  
2 2025-08-16 23:59:29 1755381569 0 "mb-mil101: GPU Usage"  
3 2025-08-16 23:58:46 1755381526 193 "mb-mil101: Check Power"  
4 2025-08-16 23:57:58 1755381478 4.271 "mb-mil101: GPU 1 Power in decaWatts"  
5 2025-08-16 23:57:57 1755381477 4.384 "mb-mil101: GPU 0 Power in decaWatts"  
6 2025-08-16 23:57:04 1755381424 198 "mb-mil101: Check Power"  
7 2025-08-16 23:55:27 1755381327 205 "mb-mil101: Check Power"  
8 ...
```

Listing 10: GPU and host power measurements.


```

1 with open(out_file_path)as out_file:
2     out_lines=out_file.readlines()
3 with open(power_file_path) as log_file:
4     log_lines=log_file.readlines()
5 summary=[]
6 for backend in backends:
7     for process in processes:
8         process_name = process.replace(' ',
9         ↪ '').replace('>', '_').replace('~', 'x')
9     for p_val in p_values:
10        start_time=None
11        end_time=None
12        for line in out_lines:
13            if m:=start_pattern.search(line):
14                p,proc,bc,ts_str=m.groups()
15                if int(p) == p_val and proc == process_name and
16                ↪ bc==backend:
17                    start_time=datetime.strptime(ts_str,
18                    "%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S")
19
20            if m:=end_pattern.search(line):
21                p,proc,bc,ts_str=m.groups()
22                if int(p) == p_val and proc == process_name and
23                ↪ bc==backend:
24                    end_time=datetime.strptime(ts_str,
25                    "%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S")
26
27            if start_time and end_time:
28                break
29        elapsed_time=(end_time-start_time).total_seconds()
30        summary.append([backend,process_name,p_val,start_time,end_time,
31        ↪ elapsed_time])
32
33        power_data=[]
34        for line in log_lines:
35            if m:=power_pattern.search(line):
36                time_str,power_str=m.groups()
37                time=datetime.strptime(time_str,"%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")
38                print('time is ',time)
39                print('start time is',start_time,'and end time
40                ↪ is',end_time)
41                if start_time<=time<=end_time:
42                    delta=(time-start_time).total_seconds()
43                    power_data.append((delta,int(power_str)))
44
45    ##write to a csv file

```

Listing 11: Power and elapsed time separation from log files.

5 Measuring the energy from power draw

Integrating the power draw over time gives the energy consumption. So we can use the plot of, e.g., the GPU power, (see Fig. 3) to calculate the energy consumed by the GPU in that run. The idle power of the GPU was subtracted to get the net power draw. In the CPU case, the idle power was calculated by taking measurements at the beginning and end of the run, where no workload was run, and then taking the average of these measurements as shown in line 13 of Listing 12. The lower and higher limit of 700 W and 740 W for the CPU power as mentioned in line 11 of Listing 12 were decided by observing the plot in Fig. 4.

```

1  with open(gpu_file_path, "r") as f:
2      reader = csv.reader(f)
3      for row in reader:
4          pwr = float(row[3])
5          gpu_power.append(pwr-24)
6
7  with open(cpu_file_path, "r") as f:
8      reader=csv.reader(f)
9      for row in reader:
10         power_cpu=float(row[2])
11         if 700<=power_cpu<=740:
12             cpu_power_limit.append(power_cpu)
13 average_cpu=sum(cpu_power_limit)/len(cpu_power_limit)
14
15 with open(cpu_file_path, "r") as f:
16     reader=csv.reader(f)
17     for row in reader:
18         power_cpu=float(row[2])
19         cpu_power.append(power_cpu - average_cpu)
20
21 Energy_gpu=(np.trapz(gpu_power,gpu_elapsed))/3600000 ##Energy in kWh
22 Energy_cpu=np.trapz(cpu_power,cpu_elapsed)/3600000 ##Energy in kWh
23 Total_energy=Energy_gpu+Energy_cpu

```

Listing 12: Energy calculation from power draw.

6 Conclusions and Outlook

In this work, we prepared the complete infrastructure necessary to perform consistent power measurements of event generation in MadGraph. We developed scripts to separate GPU and CPU power usage on the cluster, enabling us to precisely attribute power consumption to different computational backends. We also implemented tools to calculate the energy consumption in kWh, providing a reliable basis for further analysis.

Throughout the process, we have overcome challenges related to synchronizing log files with power measurements and automating workflows across different backends. Initial measurements have already been carried out, demonstrating the functionality of the framework. The produced

codes have been uploaded to a public github repository [10] and shared with the members of IT-FTI-PSE section, who will continue the project by performing further measurements and analyzing the data.

The next steps will focus on systematically analyzing the collected data, computing the net energy consumption for various processes and backends, and extending the analysis to estimate the corresponding CO₂ emissions using electricity maps [11] as shown in Fig. 5. These maps report the amount of CO₂ emissions per kWh, which can then be used to calculate the total CO₂ emissions associated with the measured energy consumption, for example by using [12].

In summary, the groundwork for sustainable performance evaluation in high-energy physics simulations has been established, and the upcoming analysis will provide valuable insights into both computational efficiency and environmental impact.

Figure 5: Screenshot from Electricity map website [11].

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